

with 1.0 kg a.i./ha (Cartap was an exception). That indicates impending BPH resurgence when low dosages of granular insecticides are applied to the rice crop (regardless of whether the low doses were due to economic limitations, defective distribution, or dilution by rains shortly after application). □

Identification of insecticides that induce brown planthopper resurgence when applied as foliar spray

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Field and insectary experiments at IRRI have consistently shown that foliar spraying of rice with insecticides such as methyl parathion, decamethrin, and diazinon induces brown planthopper (BPH) resurgence after the insecticide's toxicity is lost. Detailed studies of BPH resurgence by the authors revealed that the reproductive rate of BPH on plants protected with different insecticides would be an appropriate criterion in evaluating an insecticide's resurgence potential. Following this technique, 23 common emulsifiable concentrates of insecticides were evaluated under controlled conditions.

Among the four classes of insecticides tested, organophosphates and synthetic pyrethroids generally tended to cause resurgence, while carbamates and organochlorines were fairly safe (see table). But there were exceptions in both groups. Screening studies suggested that A 47171, FMC 35001, vamidothion, BPMC, and Perthane reduced the BPH reproductive rate significantly. Perthane, BPMC, and A 47171 have been identified as effective for BPH control in both laboratory and field experiments at IRRI. The fact that they do not cause resurgence may make them more important for BPH control. On the other hand, this evaluation also suggested that the use of methyl parathion, fenitrothion, decamethrin, diazinon, and fenthion should be avoided in BPH-infested areas because they stimulate BPH reproduction. □

Reproduction of and damage by brown planthopper as influenced by type and rate of granular insecticides applied to potted rice plants.^a

Treatment ^b	Insecticide rate (kg a.i./ha)	Nymphs ^c (no.)	No. of days for complete hopperburning ^d
Diazinon	1.0	305.3 b	16.0 bc
Diazinon	0.5	379.3 a	14.0 abc
Cartap	1.0	388.7 a	13.7 ab
Cartap	0.5	249.0 bcd	11.0 a
Aldicarb	1.0	202.7 de	17.7 cd
Aldicarb	0.5	316.7 ab	15.3 bc
Dacamox	1.0	247.0 bcd	24.7 fg
Dacamox	0.5	277.7 bc	23.3 efg
Carbofuran	1.0	189.7 d	26.7 g
Carbofuran	0.5	213.7 cd	24.7 fg
FMC 31768	1.0	137.7 e	25.0 fg
FMC 31768	0.5	187.3 d	22.7 ef
Control	—	234.7 cd	20.7 de

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^b Granules were incorporated into the soil twice when the plants were 35 and 47 days old.

^c From eggs laid by 2 females/7 days, 30 days after second application of granules.

^d Damage by nymphs that emerged from eggs laid by 2 females. Days from the emergence of first group of nymphs.

Reproductive rate of brown planthopper as influenced by various insecticides applied as foliar spray on rice. IRRI, 1978.

Treatment ^a	Formulation EC (%)	Class ^b	Reproductive rate ^c (no. of nymphs)
A47171	24	OP	107.0 a
FMC 35001	48	C	115.3 a
Vamidothion	40	OP	116.7 a
BPMC	50	C	120.0 a
Perthane	45	OC	124.7 a
Carbophenothion	40	OP	135.0 ab
FMC 27289	48	C	155.7 abc
FMC 31768	23	C	161.0 abc
Endosulfan	35	OC	182.3 abcd
Control (water spray)	—	—	207.3 bcde
Acephate	40	OP	210.7 bcde
Phosphamidon	50	OP	211.3 bcde
Methomyl	19.3	C	214.0 cde
Azinphos ethyl	40	OP	236.7 def
AC 64475	25	OP	252.3 defg
Dacamox	23	OP	253.3 efg
Cypermethrin	40	P	255.7 efg
Triazophos	40	OP	262.7 efg
Monocrotophos	16.8	OP	269.0 efg
Methyl parathion	50	OP	297.0 fghij
Fenitrothion	20	OP	322.0 ghij
Decamethrin	2.5	P	334.7 hij
Diazinon	20	OP	336.0 ij
Fenthion	50	OP	353.0 j

^a Insecticides applied as a foliar spray 3 times on plants at 20-, 30-, and 40-days after sowing at 0.04% concentration except cypermethrin and decamethrin, which were sprayed at 0.00270 concentration.

^b C = carbamate, OC = organochlorine, OP = organophosphate, P = pyrethroid.

^c From eggs laid by 2 females/7 days. The females were released 30 days after the third spraying. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.